

Teaching With and About AI Symposium

Conveners

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Preprint community

<https://zenodo.org/communities/iacap-aisb-25-teachingai>

Details

Brando's Engagement Philosophy encourages "direct engagement with our subjects of research, not only as sources of information, but as structural contributors to the development of our research projects and its priorities." This symposium applies this principle to the integration of AI in education, examining how students and educators collectively shape our understanding of AI's role in teaching and learning.

This symposium addresses a critical gap between computational and business-first approaches, offering a humanities-centered perspective on AI education that emphasises both practical application and philosophical reflection. We hope to design a volume which can discuss, with evidence, Breen's claim that in: "LLMs are deeply, inherently textual. And they are reliant on text in a way that is directly linked to the skills and methods that we emphasize in university humanities classes."

In this symposium, we will take the following chapters and present the central arguments of each. The intention of the symposium is to get flow on the connections between chapters and to get audience feedback on missing chapters or useful links between them. The volume will start with academic works by scholars, and end with student-authored case studies of their learning and insights. We will not be presenting traditional papers here, instead, we will be trying to get feedback on the volume as a whole.

We encourage audience members to review works that may interest them in the preprint community before attending.

Abstracts of the Symposium

Chapters

The Emperor's New Clothes: A Manifesto for Universities in an AI-Haunted World

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Universities face an existential crisis revealed, but not caused, by artificial intelligence. Using Lakatos' Philosophy of Science, we argue higher education has become a degenerating research programme, maintaining formal structures while abandoning educational substance. Drawing on evidence from an experimental AI-integrated unit at Macquarie University, we pose three interlocking questions: What constitutes content-increasing education when AI handles information transfer? How can universities reconnect education to meaningful world-making? What academic practices enable transformative rather than transactional learning? Student transformations documented in our unit suggest design principles for post-transactional universities that embrace productive failure, reward process mastery, and develop new capabilities beyond credentialism.

Rather than prescriptive solutions, we offer design principles derived from student experiences: rapidly transitioning between content and capability development; connecting learning to real-world impact; rewarding process mastery over outputs; embracing productive failure as pedagogy; and developing social proof beyond grades. The emperor's nakedness stands revealed. Universities must choose between maintaining elaborate fictions or embracing pedagogies suited to our AI-haunted world where students already see through credentialist illusions.

Towards an Evidence Based Framework for AI in Philosophy Education

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Widespread adoption of generative AI tools in higher education has raised questions about their appropriate role in philosophy instruction. This study investigated the comparative effectiveness of AI-assisted writing tools versus traditional writing center support in philosophy courses at two community colleges with approximately 100 participants. We tracked student performance across multiple measures including paper scores, exam performance, homework completion, and class participation. Students self-selected into using AI tools, the writing center, both, or neither for developing their term papers. Results showed that AI users performed slightly better on paper scores compared to writing center users ($p = 0.043$), though no significant differences emerged in other academic performance measures. However, qualitative analysis revealed concerning patterns in how students utilized AI, including inappropriate use for research and citation. While our findings suggest AI tools can serve complementary roles in supporting student learning when used appropriately, they also highlight the need for explicit instruction in AI literacy and careful consideration of how to preserve student agency and authentic philosophical engagement. Building on these empirical findings, we propose an ethical framework for AI integration in philosophy education centered on three principles: preserved agency, protected struggle, and demonstrated capability.

Teaching the Unknown: A Pedagogical Framework for Teaching With and About AI

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Generative artificial intelligence (AI) has disrupted education systems worldwide, exposing pre-existing pedagogical vulnerabilities while necessitating fundamental reconceptualisation of teaching practices. This disruption demands pedagogical approaches that embrace uncertainty while developing student agency amid technological indeterminacy. Traditional educational models predicated on stable knowledge transmission prove inadequate when confronting AI's emergent and probabilistic properties.

This study examined how decoupling task success from assessment outcomes created environments where students developed critical AI literacy through structured risk-taking and productive failure. Drawing on Transformative Learning Theory and Rumsfeld's epistemological Matrix as interpretive frameworks, we analysed an experimental undergraduate AI unit across three disciplinary streams: Ancient History, Philosophy, and Politics and International Relations ($N = 23$). Data collection encompassed student reflections, classroom observations, and AI interaction logs throughout a 13-week semester.

Our pedagogical framework operationalised four interconnected pillars. First, risk-embracing assessment structures valued reflection over output quality. Second, intentional classroom culture development proceeded through educator vulnerability and communal knowledge construction. Third, systematic navigation of technological uncertainty became a primary learning dimension. Fourth, facilitation of transformative learning experiences occurred through structured disorienting dilemmas. Students demonstrated measurable progression from external to internal AI locus of control, developing sophisticated understanding of when, how, and why to employ AI tools. Analysis revealed that humanities methodologies, particularly textual criticism and contextual evaluation, transfer systematically to AI contexts, challenging deficit-based professional development models.

This research presents implications across three levels: educational theory, where productive failure and epistemic uncertainty navigation challenge traditional knowledge progression models; educator praxis, recognising AI as a textual technology particularly suited to humanities expertise; and university teaching contexts, requiring new quality frameworks that prioritise process-focused assessment over demonstrable competency acquisition. Effective AI education requires sustained investment in psychological safety through formative assessment, access to frontier models rather than basic institutional offerings, and institutional support for pedagogical experimentation beyond traditional frameworks.

Ethnographic insights into AI Pedagogy for Higher Education: A Qualitative Study.

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This chapter presents findings from four months of ethnographic field work in an experimental arts capstone unit on AI at Macquarie University (2024). Guided by the research question, “*How does a university seminar on Large Language Models (LLMs) transform students' digital habitus and ethical awareness as they develop strategies for understanding and critically engaging with artificial intelligence?*” the study employs the concept of digital habitus (Romele 2023; Bourdieu 1977) to examine how the seminar facilitated a shift from students' initial apprehension, misconceptions, and mixed perceptions about AI toward technical proficiency and the development of critical ethical awareness—the capacity to reflect on the ethical implications of AI use across contexts and to make informed judgments based on critical practice.

Universities are increasingly seeking ways to integrate AI that enhance rather than erode education. Yet, quantitative global surveys paint a grim picture: only half of students regularly engage critically with AI tools and their output,

while the rest admit to complacent or inappropriate use (Gillespie et al. 2025, p.94). More than 50% report concealing their use of AI to complete coursework, and a staggering 45% presented AI-generated content as their own (Gillespie et al. 2025). These figures draw the curtain on deeper issues long present in higher education: declining student engagement, credentialism, and the hollowing out of meaningful learning (Ballson-Stunton & Torrington 2025). Educational leaders are now calling for a reimagining of the sector, urging institutions to treat AI's advance as an opportunity for transformative change (Liu & Bates 2025; Ballson-Stunton & Khaled 2025).

Amid emerging scholarship that approaches AI pedagogy as a culturally situated process (Liu & Bates 2025; Ballson-Stunton & Torrington 2025), this chapter argues for the centrality of culture in shaping both the risks and possibilities of AI integration in higher education. Drawing on ethnographic data, it grounds Ballson-Stunton and Torrington's four-pillar framework for a pedagogy of AI in students' lived experiences, offering evidence for how intentionally designed classroom cultures can cultivate transparent, critical, and responsible engagement with AI in tertiary education.

Case Studies

AI's Applicability to the Legal Profession

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Artificial intelligence's ('AI') piecemeal introduction to the law is crucial to maintaining the integrity of the legal profession. This is on account of AI's hallucinatory abilities to generate content and subsequent risks this poses in ensuring accurate legal knowledge is conveyed to the general public. The likelihood of spreading legal misinformation is further exacerbated due to systemic American biases present in current language learning models ('LLMs') – an issue encountered during my study of AI-Enabled Politics and International Relations ('ARTX3500'). It is therefore necessary that LLMs are subject to ongoing scrutiny and regulation by bodies responsible for their administration, with the impetus of eradicating inherent bias altogether. This case study will discuss insights garnered during the study of ARTX3500 concerning the use of AI in educational and personal contexts from a legal standpoint. Accrued insights assert that AI proves useful in performing administrative tasks – namely, to summarise information and plan written submissions – and thus, can be integrated into the legal profession. Use of LLMs to complete clerical processes illustrate that indeed, AI can be utilised in a manner that maintains the importance of critical thinking to the legal profession.

The Art of the Prompt: Lessons in Play, Bias, and Digital Creation

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This autoethnographic study chronicles a journey from skepticism to creative collaboration with generative AI. Initially viewing AI as a threat to authentic creativity, the author engages in playful experimentation with AI tools, exploring their potential to amplify, rather than replace, human expression. Through intentional prompting, artistic inquiry, and philosophical reflection, the study reveals that AI acts as a mirror, reflecting the depth and nuance of human input. By documenting the process of creating both visual and literary art, the research demonstrates how specific language and personal intent can yield deeply meaningful and personal outputs. Ultimately, the study identifies three pivotal insights: AI's outputs are shaped by human intentionality; meaningful collaboration with AI requires curiosity and play; and ethical creativity in this new paradigm demands transparency and acknowledgment of AI as both tool and co-creator. Ultimately, this work challenges traditional notions of authorship and creativity,

emphasizing the value of questioning biases, critically analyzing new tools, and embracing AI as a technological quill for modern artistic practice.

Grappling with uncertainty in AI use

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Trust in our tools: a spectrum of AI utility

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The unmonitored release of Large Language Models into educational contexts has created profound challenges around trust, utility, and academic integrity. This autoethnographic case study examines my personal transformation from AI sceptic to confident user, exploring how trust develops in human-AI relationships within educational settings. Drawing upon Martin Heidegger's tool analysis framework, I trace AI's evolution from "present-at-hand"—a suspicious, constantly scrutinised other—to "ready-to-hand," an intuitive extension of my academic practice.

Through reflective analysis of my experiences in an experimental AI course, I demonstrate that AI trust is context, education, and application specific. Early teachings emphasised providing rich contextual information to combat AI's hallucinatory nature. As my understanding deepened through structured experimentation, my relationship with AI shifted from fearful avoidance to confident collaboration.

Trust functions as a crucial moderator between AI integration and academic performance. When I began treating Claude as a 24/7 tutor—sharing genuine academic anxieties while maintaining ethical boundaries—the tool became ready-to-hand. My interactions evolved from formal, sceptical queries to casual conversations that maintained task focus while providing support. This transformation enabled more confident class participation, reduced procrastination, and improved learning outcomes.

Critically, this Heideggerian transformation enhanced rather than diminished my critical thinking skills. With adequate training and trust development, AI became a tool that amplified my analytical capabilities rather than replacing them. The findings suggest educational institutions should foster informed trust through structured, context-rich integration. This case study demonstrates that AI's educational value depends not on the technology itself, but on developing appropriate trust relationships and teaching effective prompting that strengthen and broaden the realm of critical thinking through effective tool use.

Rethinking the Role of AI in University Learning

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This paper presents a case study of my personal study journey of integrating artificial intelligence (AI) in university, drawing on my experiences as an international student from Hong Kong at Macquarie University (Australia). The study begins by exploring initial expectations and anxieties, shaped by limited access to AI tools in Hong Kong and general misconceptions about AI's capabilities. The narrative reveals the varied beliefs and practices surrounding AI in higher education through hands-on engagement with large language models (LLMs) and observation of peers from diverse academic and cultural backgrounds.

The findings indicate a distinct contrast in students' approaches to AI. Those with a superficial understanding tend to rely heavily on AI, often leading to lower academic performance. In contrast, students who thoughtfully utilise AI

as a supplementary resource engage critically with the technology and their subject matter, resulting in deeper learning and improved achievement. The paper examines the importance of user agency, language background, and the reciprocal relationship between user and machine in shaping the quality of AI-assisted work.

Practical strategies for effective AI use are discussed, including prompt engineering, critical verification of outputs, and leveraging AI as a collaborative thinking partner. The study also addresses ethical and philosophical questions, such as data privacy, the impact of restrictive policies like those in Hong Kong, and the need for balanced AI education that includes both technical and ethical dimensions.

The conclusion argues that AI is neither a replacement for human effort nor a threat to learning, but a tool whose value depends on thoughtful, informed engagement. Empowering students with access to AI and critical guidance is essential for preparing graduates for a future shaped by rapid technological change. This case study invites educators and policymakers to reflect on how best to integrate AI into teaching and learning responsibly and effectively.